

Physico-Chemical Studies of Thallous Complexes of Some Unsaturated Acids

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Spectrophotometric and conductometric studies reveal that thallium(I) forms 1:1 complexes with crotonic, cinnamic, citraconic and itaconic acids. Stoichiometry has been studied by monovariation and continuous variation methods. Stability constants of these complexes have been determined by Job's method and also Banerji and Dey method. From the stability constants at different temperatures, changes in free energy of formation, enthalpy and entropy changes have been calculated at $28^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$.

UNSATURATED monocarboxylic acids, excepting few, do not show much tendency towards complex formation. There is no record of complex formation by unsaturated monocarboxylic acids excepting those of crotonic acid with copper^{1,2} and cinnamic acid with thorium³. Dicarboxylic unsaturated acids are more complexing and mostly chelates are formed. Citraconate complexes of copper², calcium⁴, and strontium⁴ are known whereas only cuprous itaconate² is found in the literature.

Thallium (I) complex of crotonic, cinnamic, citraconic and itaconic acids are not cited in the literature. Author has therefore taken up the study of composition, stability and thermodynamics of these complexes.

E. Merck thallous nitrate and B. D. H. samples of the organic acids are used. As the complex is more stable in alkaline medium, sodium salts of the acids are used as ligands. B. D. H. (Analar) anhydrous sodium carbonate is used for preparing sodium salts. "DORON" conductivity bridge with dip type conductivity cell is used for measurement of conductance. Absorbance measurements are done with "Beckmann DU quartz spectrophotometer" with 0.5 cm. light path.

All mixtures were kept for 8 hrs to attain the equilibrium and measurements were carried out at temperature 28° , 38° , and $48^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$. Experimental procedures are as in our earlier publication⁶.

Stoichiometry: Compositions of the complexes were first studied by monovariation⁶ method. $M/30$ and $M/40$ equimolar solutions were mixed, each time keeping the volume of one of the components constant (5ml). Clear breaks are obtained in all the cases, exactly at 5ml of the added component (Fig. 1). This reveals the formation of 1:1 complexes with all the four ligands. Stoichiometry is further confirmed by Job's continuous variation⁷ method for equimolar solutions. $M/40$, $M/60$, and $M/80$ equimolar solutions were used.

Fig. 1

A - $\frac{M}{30}$ Na-cinnamate, B - $\frac{M}{30}$ Na-crotonate,

C - $\frac{M}{30}$ Na-citraconate, D - $\frac{M}{40}$ Na-itaconate,

Three sets of readings were taken with each ligand. Maxima are obtained exactly at 50% each of the metal and ligand solutions, confirming 1:1 composition of the complexes. Continuous variation method was studied both with conductance and absorbance. (Figs. 2 and 3).

Fig. 2

A - $\frac{M}{40}$ Na-cinnamate, B - $\frac{M}{100}$ Na-crotonate,
 C - $\frac{M}{40}$ Na-citraconate, D - $\frac{M}{40}$ Na-itaconate,

Stability: Stabilities of these complexes are determined by Job's method and also Banerji and Dey⁸ method. Job's method was studied by conductance and absorbance whereas Banerji and Dey method was applied to spectrophotometry. For conductometric work $M/60$, $M/80$, and $M/100$ ligand solutions were mixed with $M/40$ metal solution. For spectrophotometric work, excepting for cinnamate, $M/200$ metal and $M/100$ ligand solutions were used. For cinnamate $M/2000$ metal and $M/1000$ ligand solutions were used. Optical density measurements were done at wavelengths 250 nm to 310 nm, depending upon the maximum divergence ($\Delta - 0.D$) for different complexes.

The stability measurements were first done at a temperature of 28°. Same set of mixtures of solutions were subjected in a thermostat to two higher temperatures (38° and 48°) with an accuracy of $\pm 0.5^\circ$. The values of Log K calculated for these complexes are as below :

Complex	LogK		
	28°	38°	48°
1. Thallous-crotonate	1.30	1.74	1.70
2. Thallous-cinnamate	1.50	1.44	1.40
3. Thallous-citraconate	1.84	1.79	1.76
4. Thallous-itaconate	1.66	1.59	1.57

Thermodynamics: From the stability constants the changes in free energy ΔF were evaluated with the help of the equation :

$$\Delta F = -RT \ln K$$

Enthalpy and entropy changes of these complexes were calculated as usual making use of the following relations :

$$\text{Log } K_1 - \text{Log } K_2 = - \frac{\Delta H}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_1} - \frac{1}{T_2} \right)$$

$$\text{and } \Delta G = \Delta H - T\Delta S$$

The values are tabulated below :

Complex	ΔG Kcal/mole	ΔH Kcal/mole	ΔS Cals/degree/mole
1. Thallous-crotonate	-2.47	-13.00	-51.42
2. ,, -cinnamate	-2.06	-13.12	-50.43
3. ,, -citraconate	-2.56	-12.99	-51.65
4. ,, -itaconate	-2.22	-13.06	-50.97

Discussions

Citraconic acid (methyl maleic acid) and itaconic acid (an isomer of citraconic acid) are unsaturated dicarboxylic acids and behave like bidentate ligands. Thallous citraconate shows greater stability as compared to thallous itaconate. Both form seven membered ring with thallous ion but the lesser stability of itaconate complex may be due to the presence of double bond in the ring. The greater stability of citraconate is perhaps due to the pronounced polar effect caused by the double bond in it.

Fig. 3

A - $\frac{M}{1000}$ Na-cinnamate, B - $\frac{M}{100}$ Na-crotonate,
 C - $\frac{M}{100}$ Na-citraconate, D - $\frac{M}{100}$ Na-itaconate,

Crotonic and cinnamic acids are unsaturated mono-carboxylic acids. Thallous-crotonate is more stable as compared to cinnamate. The lesser stability of cinnamate complex may be due to the introduction of a heavy benzene nucleus in place of methyl group (in crotonic acid), and hence weakening the metal ligand bond.

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